

TECH TRANSFER MECHANISMS FOR COMPOSITE MANUFACTURING FROM UNIVERSITIES TO INDUSTRY - A SURVEY OF SUCCESSFUL MODELS

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SUMMARY: There has been a significant investment in Universities for research into advanced materials synthesis, design and processing. What has been lacking has been an efficient system to commercialize the results of this research funding. Technology transfer is more than licensing or turning over information, especially for composites. This paper will present successful case histories.

Technology development and transfer, as it is more broadly practiced, is a process.... a process of establishing relationships along the development cycle. In order to consider the adoption of technology development process as an operating strategy for technology transfer, any organization - university, business - requires: an ability to characterize the development cycle and define its role in a success; a team based management style based on trust; and an ability to integrate the "voice of the customer" in setting operating priorities.

KEYWORDS: technology transfer, knowledge-based economy, research organizations

UNIVERSITY - INDUSTRY TECHNOLOGY TRANSFER PROCESS

Product Development Cycle

A successful product development process is characterized by an understanding of the research and development process; and a reorganization to meet the needs of an information based economy.

Commercialization pathways for basic research in the United States vary in their design and in their success. The majority of \$250 billion spent on research and development, some estimate 85-90% of the R&D budget, is applied to solving problems with existing products [1]. Most of the estimated 10-15 % left for basic discovery research is spent at Universities and US Federal Labs. The Industrial share of basic research is less than 20 % of the Federal budget. This varies by technology - from 20% for biotechnology to 10% for composites.

The investment from the Federal Government has resulted in the creation of the largest research engine in the world. However, in the last decade it became evident that the US lacked a transmission for this engine - an innovation transmission. The US lacked an efficient mechanism to transfer the basic research results from the university and federal labs. One study found that companies in Japan and the United States are roughly equally fast to market with internally generated ideas, but Japanese companies are almost twice as fast to market with externally generated ideas--U.S. companies much slower [2].

Eventhough the US had the competitive advantage of the enormous basic research capacity, basic discoveries are a long way from commercialization. The risk capital required for commercialization is 10 to 100 times that required for the basic concept development. In a study for a Consumer Products Company by Battelle, they found that it took \$5.7 million to recover the cost of developing the wining idea plus another \$9.3 million for culling out losing ideas along the way [3].

It takes 7 to 10 years for the innovation process to translate a basic research discovery into a set of commercial products that then create sales and profits. Every organization in the technology transfer process should understand how research projects are initiated, continued, killed, or commercialized. Most U.S. companies organize the commercial development process either as:

- the "build a better mousetrap" approach - which assumes the customer will buy the improved mousetrap if it is priced right, even if there is no need; or the "flash of genius"; or
- "another Xerox" approach - which assumes a unique individual will discover a solution that overwhelms or creates a market, ignoring the cost of supporting the genius until a discovery is generated [4].

Projects are demanded by the marketing organization and handed to the customer with little or no involvement. Research agenda are reactive to production problems or competition.

Most university research agendas are set by individual faculty who investigate problems either based on curiosity or potential for peer recognition. The federal laboratories have their research agenda defined by the strategic defense of the nation, potential for peer recognition, or by legislative edict.

Figure 1 characterizes the traditional commercialization process as a "funnel". New concepts are generated by basic research centers; transferred to the applied development centers using publications; where, possibly, investment is made to generate prototypes and consequently products. The "funnel" becomes narrower closer to the market place, as concepts are filtered out according to various sets of criteria - mostly financial [5].

Figure 1. Development Cycle

The other factor mentioned for the relative lack of success in the innovation is the inability of traditional organizations to modify themselves for the new "knowledge based" economy, applying old hierarchical structures used in commodity based economies. There are two

distinct types of "industry" - commodity-based and information /knowledge based. Manufacturing is now uncoupled from labor and non renewable resources. From 1973 to 1985 manufacturing increased 40% in production, and did so with five million fewer people. It is forecasted that by the year 2010, only 10% of the labor force will be involved in manufacturing, which is a potential loss of six million jobs. Manufacturers are substituting knowledge and capital for labor.

In some industries, the largest contributor to cost now is overhead. The engineering or knowledge content of products is uncoupling manufacturing from scarce resources. Today 50 pounds of fiber optics carry more information than one ton of copper wire, and require one tenth of the energy to produce. Semiconductor chips only require 12% labor, but 70% knowledge; and in pharmaceutical, there is only 15% labor, and 50% knowledge content [6].

In traditional organizations, the market or customers do not have much input on the research agenda or the criteria used to screen projects as they move through the "funnel". Most developmental dollars are spent at the end of a project - right before commercialization or after the first order, the best chance to correct earlier "misunderstandings" - not at the beginning where it would have the most value. It is difficult to justify expenditures of today's cash on tomorrow's market promises and a preliminary understanding of the technical barriers, the scientist and the business manager need to develop a market-driven screening method. Preferably one that combines qualitative measurements of the potential technical and commercial difficulties; with the forecasted quantitative costs of development and the return on that investment.

The "New" Knowledge-Based Development Organizations

A number of organizations, both businesses and universities, are now in a period of transition where they are attempting to learn how to implement a market driven research agenda even at the basic discovery level and then to expedite the knowledge transfer process to become "fast to market". The first step for any organization to seek the "voice of the customer" is to realize that that the basic processes of businesses have changed. Now it is mass customization, knowledge based products, activity based costing, and the virtual corporation. The "new" organization needs to define who the "customers" are and what are their expectations. Finally, these "new" organizations determine if the existing organizational structure needs to be thrown out, modified, or optimized.

Most existing development organizations are organized around a hierarchical structure that started thousands of years ago in the Chinese Empire and, was improved by the Romans. In those days, information transition was measured in months, and could be easily compartmentalized. Hierarchy established power by controlling access [7]. Now, with local area networks, electronic mail, computer data bases, and CNN, every employee has as much information as the CEO. "Global" organizations utilize their ability to move information across national boundaries, and then modify it locally to implement a regional development strategy. The role/paradigm of management has changed from information channlers and samplers of work to facilitators - leaders that define the vision and then get out of the way.

The competitive battles looming ahead will be based upon speed - "fast to market" - and expanding the corporate imagination - developing new markets that do not exist today. "Fast to market" companies are aware of the latest technologies. They willing to risk development capital based on preliminary justification developed in a team environment [8]. "Fast to

market" organizations expand the "funnel" - expand the corporate imagination - with a "window" on technology. A "window" on technology should be able to scan the basic scientific work at University Laboratories to screen technology opportunities at the concept or proof of concept stage. These organizations ask of the results of basic research are: *derivative* - problem solving for existing products or processes; or, *platform* - involve significant product/process changes but not with new technologies; or *breakthrough* - establishment of new core products or processes often defining new markets by their creation. "Fast to market" organizations are new but have demonstrated real value. AT&T reduced the design cycle for its 4200 cordless phone from two years to one year. They achieved: lower costs, higher quality, and one additional year of sales income [9].

“New” University Organizations

Universities are reorganizing their Technology Transfer/Commercialization functions to recognize the value of industrial collaboration and their role in the national economic development policy. More than 100 U.S. Universities have started financing new companies to commercialize faculty discoveries and to promote regional economic development. In 1985, MIT began to target small growth business for licensing of University technology. Now over 60% of their license agreements are with small companies, and eight percent are with new companies created around the technology. Patent applications have doubled because of these efforts, and it has had a profound effect on the state economy. The Bank of Boston has estimated that 636 business started by MIT Alumni and faculty have generated more than 300,000 jobs in the state of Massachusetts and at least \$10 billion in annual income [10].

The United States university intellectual property market, as reported by the Association of University Technology Managers, increased to \$422 million in FY 1994, an 11% increase over FY 1993. This is double what was received in FY 1991. The number of licenses increased to 2,484 in FY 1994, a 63% increase in activity since FY 1991. Universities are becoming more aggressive in their marketing efforts. They are hiring more personnel -- the number of advertised positions for tech transfer associates has increased 50% in the last two years. Universities are actively seeking industrial partners.

Industry is also actively seeking university technology. However, each participant in the market must deal with the reality of different cultures but similar pressures: changing funding, aging demographics, hierarchy moving to team based organizations, and global competitors. Universities and industry do view the world differently. Each has a different reward system; set research priorities according to different criteria; and even have a different measure of time as shown in the following matrix.

	University View	Industry View
Rewards	Grad. Students, Facilities, Salary, Peer Recognition	Profit, Bonuses, Standard of Living
Research Priorities	Peers, Curiosity	Market, Executives
Values	Freedom, Collaboration, Openness	Independence, Competition, Risk Reduction
Time	Semesters, Ph.D. Cycle	Weeks, Annual

The barriers to collaboration or licensing from a university that companies mention most often are:

- Lack of understanding by the faculty of the value of protecting technology.
- Most faculty know-how is difficult to access. Written records can be faulty or missing.
- Technology is overvalued by faculty, especially for early stage discoveries.
- University administration focused on the deal, not the relationship.

Lack of a realistic appraisal of time, facilities, and capital required for commercialization.

The cooperation that other global competitors enjoyed with their governments and universities prompted the establishment of a number of opportunities for partnership at the basic and applied research level. Significant government actions include:

- National Cooperative Research and Development Act of 1984, allows firms to jointly fund and/or conduct "pre-competitive" research. For example, the Automotive Composite Consortium (ACC) was formed by Chrysler, Ford, and General Motors to develop large structural polymer composite parts at high production rates.
- Federal Centers of Excellence, now NSF and Department of Defense research center funding requires technology transfer, especially small businesses. Two examples are the S/I/U/CRC Low Cost, High Speed Composite Processing Center at Michigan State University and the NSF Science and Technology Center on High Performance Polymeric Adhesives and Composites at Virginia Tech.

COMPOSITES DEVELOPMENT ORGANIZATIONS

Commercial Composite Development

The materials industry development structure, which is the basis of the composites industry, has some characteristics which are a combination of history and the capital requirement for production. When new materials are synthesized either at a University research center or in a corporate lab, they must be mixed with additives to make them useful for the targeted applications. The composites industry is structured into:

1. Basic Materials Suppliers - Large Chemical companies that synthesize and or polymerize materials; for the
2. Compounders or Formulators - Combination of small and large companies that blend materials to meet specific market needs; from the
3. End users - Combination of small and large companies that design, fabricate and or add value to manufactured parts with advanced materials.

A number of composites end users are entering into new collaborations because the traditional approaches have not generated the necessary goals of low cost parts with high structural performance. Composites have always been attractive to the aerospace industry because of their weight to performance ratio to metals. The US government and the commercial aircraft industry have invested significant moneys to realize these properties but growth has been limited because of cost. Some aerospace company have invested in alternative organizations to combine their knowledge of high performance with Automotive knowledge of low cost commercial manufacturing techniques. As an example, Northrop Grumman acquired Ticom,

a directed preform and custom molding automotive RTM parts manufacturer, and became a prime contractor for the Advance Technology Transit Bus Project. Both have provided new technology for the core businesses to utilize at a lower costs and in less time to transfer the knowledge as depicted in figure 2 [11]

Fig 2. Goal of Composites Research Programs

University Composites Development

Industry involvement in Composites research at Universities occurs in three levels: 1) - industry affiliate; 2) - Industrial/Government Consortium; and 3) - Industry Advisory Board at a Engineering Research Center or Science and Technology Center. Typically in an industrial affiliate program, a firm joins for a set fee and then is granted a variety of rights, ranging from: newsletters, to regular research review meetings, to access to professors for consulting and students for hiring; to review of research proposals; to advising on research agenda, to intellectual property. MIT has approximately 11 industrial affiliates programs with 1 in the materials area. Eight companies are in the Materials Affiliates program and they review research proposals. Stanford has 34 industrial programs with one in the materials area. 15 companies are in the materials industrial affiliation and they attend one annual two meeting.

NSF currently supports 18 Engineering Research Centers, 52 Industry University Cooperative Research Centers, and 10 recently developed State Industry University Cooperative Research Centers. The idea was to increase the level of cooperation between industry and the university by leveraging State and Federal money with industry and with that commitment gain direct involvement.

An example of University/Industry interaction is the work of Dr. Ken Reifsnider - Alexander Giacco Professor of Engineering Science and Mechanics; Director, Center for Composite Materials and Structures; and Director, Virginia Commonwealth Center for Material Systems. Dr. Reifsnider is originator of the MRLife performance simulation code for the prediction of remaining strength and life. That code has been used by many major industries to estimate the durability and damage tolerance of composite materials and structures, especially under complex loading and environmental conditions such as high temperature service in aggressive

environments. The code is being integrated into the design codes of industries, including Babcock and Wilcox, General Electric, United Technologies, and others.

This work has also resulted in the spin off of Durability, Inc. This small business, located in the Corporate Research Park at Virginia Tech, provides material characterization, design, and analysis of composite material systems. Corporations can choose where it is most efficient to conduct life cycle research for composites. Either on the university campus as part of the MRLife consortium or off campus in a small business. The university and the Commonwealth of Virginia win in either instance. If the company elects to fund the work on campus then additional basic research is conducted and the education of graduate students is funded who can become future employees. If the work is funded at Durability, the class room of Dr. Reifsnider is enriched with real world experience, plus employment opportunities are created for graduates of Virginia Tech.

Virginia Tech Intellectual Properties, Inc. - "New" Development Organization for Composites

Traditional technology transfer is based on the belief that a University exists only to educate students; obtain research grants; and to publish papers. Therefore, patents are a hindrance and research funding by industry is a defacto conflict of interest. Traditional technology transfer consists of:

- Faculty develop areas of expertise based on obtaining federal funds in a competitive proposal process where the research agenda is established in a review by their peers.
- Commercial interests will read peer reviewed articles and identify the "best" science to fund to continue development, as long as it does not become too applied, and will then pay the University a license to practice the patents.
- Administration will periodically publish a list of patents or technologies under development, and commercial interests will contact them to negotiate a license

Virginia Tech Intellectual Properties, Inc. (VTIP) was formed in 1985 to identify, legally protect, and market intellectual properties resulting from research at Virginia Tech which have the potential of becoming commercially attractive technology. VTIP was also charged with being financially self-sufficient after sharing royalties with the inventors according to the University's Intellectual Property Policy. After a decade of success, VTIP is growing and changing to ensure further successes, adopting a more proactive effort to generate opportunities for license negotiations and income. VTIP brings some unique competitive advantages to this market.

1. *Equity in Lieu of License Fee and/or Patent Expense.* All start-ups have one thing in common. They don't have enough cash. VTIP has directly taken equity in lieu of license fees and/or patent expenses in three firms and indirectly in three more firms. One has gone public and another is on track with a second round of financing.
2. *Incubation of For-profit Subsidiary.* VTLS was a for profit subsidiary of VTIP that to commercialized a software technology. VTIP brought access to the technology and provided a financial umbrella. The inventor brought an existing customer base and a will to win. The exit scenario was a management buyout with an IRR of 25% to VTIP.
3. *Investment in Seed Venture Capital.* The probability of institutional investment is inversely proportional to the distance that the fund managing partner must travel. VTIP

along with the Virginia Tech Foundation, has invested in Zero Stage, Triad/University Partners, InterSouth, and SpaceVest. These investments in seed venture capital provide excellent opportunities for Virginia Tech start-ups to present their business plans.

4. *Investment in "Bridge Funding"*. VTIP, along with Johns Hopkins and some private investors, funded Triad which invests in early stage technologies. Technologies that have significant potential but are too early stage to attract commercial interest. An example is the work of Dr. Judy Riffle and Dr. Jack Lesko - "Thermoplastic Sizing for Carbon Fiber Composites". Dr. Riffle and Dr. Lesko have developed various sizings for carbon fiber reinforced composites with vinyl ester matrices. These composites offer cost advantages relative to epoxy matrices as well as better environmental stability. But in which part of the materials developmental chain should it be licensed in order to attract the risk capital for development - the fiber company, or the resin company, or the compounder, or the parts fabricator. Triad provided the risk capital to further development. Now patents are being prosecuted and licensees are being sought.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Additional development capacity for the university can be gained through strategic alliances, partnerships, joint ventures and consortiums with other research centers. Once the mission of the various research partners is defined, then the appropriate technology development organization can be implemented to achieve its unique growth plan. The strategic direction will define the effective research mix for the resources available and will determine the need for leverage for partnerships. It will also be the first screen for new ideas. Technology Development and Transfer is not a threat to intellectual freedom; but a catalyst for a university to recognize its total contribution to the creation of wealth in a state economy. Faculty would increase their choices for implementation of their discoveries and would identify new colleges that had not been available to them. New technology transfer mechanisms from the largest research engine in the world provide significant opportunities for U.S. businesses to "leap frog" their global competitors.

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